

leaf extract. At 14 d after inoculation, they were scored for resistance using the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*. Of 117 entries, 26 were resistant (see table). For the remaining 91, susceptibility ranged from moderate to high. *ℳ*

Varietal reaction to BB at IAAS, Rampur, Nepal, 1985.

Cultivar	Score ^a
Tetep	1.0
BG379-2	1.0
Nigeria 5	1.0
DV85	1.0
IR19661-63-1-2-3	1.0
BG400-1	3.0
IR8608-82-1-3-1-3	3.0
C 1321-9	3.0
ADT36	3.0
BPT3291	3.0
IR19083-22-2-2	3.0
Taichung Sen 1	3.0
BR153-21-10-1-3	3.0
Se 322B-19	3.0
BG367-4	3.0
IR2307-247-2-2-3	3.0
IR5873-9-1	3.0
IR50	3.0
IR9171-60-2-2	3.0
IR2725-63-2-2	3.0
IR36	3.0
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	3.0
Chainung Sen Yu 29	3.0
IR62	3.0
Thapani	3.0
Saeto Anadi	3.0
TN1 (check)	9.0

^aBy the 1980 SES scale.

Genetic divergence and multiple disease resistance studies in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Genetic divergence is one criterion in selecting parents to generate crosses that give transgressive segregants in later generations. A parental divergence study was undertaken with released varieties and 120 elite lines (94 semidwarf, 24 intermediate, and 2 tall) primarily selected for their bacterial blight (BB) tolerance. The lines were from IRRI (55), India (42), Bangladesh (10),

Indonesia (5), 2 each from USA, Taiwan, and Sri Lanka, and 1 each from Thailand and the Philippines. The crop was grown under recommended agronomic practices in 1977 wet season (WS) at Pantnagar in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line had a 4-m² plot and 20- × 15-cm spacing. Mahalanobis D² statistics was used to study genetic divergence based on six characters: day to 50% flowering, plant height, effective tillers per plant, grain weight, grains per panicle, and grain yield (14% moisture) per plot. The lines were grouped in 18 clusters per Tocher's method suggested by Rao.

The lines were also screened for BB resistance in WS 1977, 1978, and 1979 at Pantnagar (29°N, 79.3°E, and 243.8 m mean sea level); for leaf blast at Majhera District, Nainital, in hills (29.28°N, 79.32° E, and 900 m); and for brown spot at Ranichauri (30.18°N, 78.290° E, and 2000 m) using the *Standard*

evaluation system for rice scale. Eleven lines showed multiple resistance to all three diseases.

Clustering pattern revealed five clusters (see table). One or two lines were further selected from each cluster on the basis of their higher grain yield, effective tillers, grain weight, hulling and milling percentage, and desirable alkali digestion value. IR2070-414-3-9 and BGW-2 in cluster I, IR22 in cluster V, and IR2415-904-3 in cluster VII were most desirable. The intercluster distance revealed that cluster VIII and IX were most divergent, followed by V and VIII, and VII and IX. BKN68 19-33-3-2-1-3 and IR2328-300-2-2 had higher divergence than most entries. The cross combination IR2328-300-2-2 and BKN6819-33-3-2-1-3 had maximum divergence followed by IR22 and IR2328-300-2-2. These crosses can be used to further select recombinants with multiple resistance, higher yield, and other desirable traits. *ℳ*

Intracluster and intercluster D² value in 5 selected clusters and the multiple-resistance lines in each cluster. 1977-79, Bihar, India.

Cluster	D ² value in different clusters					Multiple-resistance lines
	I	V	VII	VIII	IX	
I	28.2	75.7	51.5	188.0	152.0	IR2070-414-3-9 BG90-2 RP633-519-1-3-4-1 IR2071-527-3-1-3 IR2328-27-3-6 IR22
V		36.3	134.2	380.7	216.6	IR2415-90-4-3 IR2863-39-2 IR5491-4-80
VII			24.6	99.8	272.4	IR2328-300-2-2 IR2328-300-2-2
VIII				28.7	449.7	BKN6819-33-3-2-1-3
IX					13.9	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Promising rice cultivars with combined resistance to gall midge (GM) and brown planthopper (BPH)

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Breeding for multiple resistance to pests is being emphasized for yield stability in

modern varieties. In 1984 kharif (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov), we evaluated 45 entries from the AICRIP 1983 multiple resistance screening trial against GM in the field. Outbreak conditions were induced by close spacing (10 × 15 cm), adjusting planting time to 20 Jul to coincide with maximum infestation of the season, applying high N rates (100 + 25 + 25 g N/ha at 0, 15, and 30 d after

Promising entries from the multiple resistance screening trial against GM and BPH. Cuttack, India, 1983 kharif.

Entry	Silvershoots (%)	GM-infested hills (%)	BPH resistance score ^a
RP2068-18-3-5	0	0	1
RP2068-17-3-7	0	0	7
RP2068-18-4-5	0	0	3
RP2068-18-2-6	0	0	7
RP2068-16-9-5	0	0	9
RP2068-18-4-7	0	0	9
Rp2068-18-2-11	0	4	7
TN1	40	100	9
IET8868 (OR 405-4)	0	0	7
IET7800	0	0	—
IET8371	0	0	1
RP2199-84-2	4	4	7
IR4707-106-3-2	29	77	7
RP2071-18-1-1	48	96	3
RP2076-464-2	40	92	3
TN1	26	100	9
RP2069-34-1-2	40	96	3
RP2068-12-1-8-1	28	96	1
RP2068-15-1-4-2	0	0	7
RP1579-28	0	0	9
RP1579-43	0	0	—
RP1579-48	4	4	7
RP1579-53	0	0	9
TN1	32	100	9

^aBy SES.

transplanting), and installing lights. Damage (% silvershoots and % infested hills) was graded when infestation peaked.

The same entries were tested for BPH resistance in the greenhouse by the bulk seedling screening method. Damage was graded on the 0–9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Thirteen cultivars were highly resistant to GM (see table). Three cultivars — RP2068-18-2-11, RP2199-84-2, and RP1579-48 — had less than 5% infestation. A strong correlation was observed between percentage of silvershoots and percentage of infested hills ($r = 0.786$).

Seven entries were resistant to BPH (score 1–3): and three — RP2068-18-3-5, RP2068-4-4-5, and IET8371 — were resistant to both GM and BPH. The RP2068 cultivars were derived from the cross Swarnadhan/ Veluthachem, while IET8371 came from the cross Phalguna/ARC6650, deriving their dual resistance from known donors. *ℵ*

Varietal resistance of rice to leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a major pest in India, causing 80% yield loss in rice. We screened 18 rice accessions from AICRIP for resistance to leaffolder by a seedling screening technique at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, and in field trials at Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondichery, during 1984 kharif.

Pregerminated seeds of test accessions were sown 6 cm apart in 6 rows in 50 × 40 × 10 cm wooden seedboxes. Each accession was planted in a replication across the width of the seedbox in such a way to maintain at least 5 hills (3 plants/hill) per row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and two rows with resistant checks ASD11 and PTB33 were sown at random in the seedboxes.

Leaffolder resistance in rice accessions.

Rice accession	Cross/Parents	Damage rating	
		Glasshouse (Coimbatore)	Field (Pondicherry)
RP 2068-18-2-9	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	3	1
RP 2068-184-2	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	5	3
RP 2068-18-4-5	Swarnadhan/Veluthachera	3	3
IR4707-106-3-2	IR1888-156/IR2061-213-2	3	3
	IR1561-228-3-3		
Bangelei	Donor	5	3
ARC 6650	Donor	3	3
CO 29	Donor	5	3
PTB 12	Donor	5	3
TNAU LFR831333	Vaigai/ARC 10550	5	3
TNAU LFR832036	IR20/ARC 10550	3	1
TNAU LFR832038	IR20/Vazhaippoo Samba	5	3
TNAU LFR831311	CO 41/BKNBR1088-83	3	1
TNAU LFR832035	CO 41/BKNBR1088-83	3	3
TNAU LFR831331	Bhavani/T2005	3	3
ARC10660	Donor	3	3
W 1263	Donor	5	1
TKM 6	Donor	5	3
IET 5741	Imp. Sab./Sona	3	3
ASD11	(Resistant check)	3	—
FTB33	(Resistant check)	3	—
TN1	(Susceptible check)	9	5

On the 7th day of seeding the wooden seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (62 × 47 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm of water. Twenty days after seeding, the plants in the seedboxes were covered

with rectangular nylon net cages into which field-collected leaffolder moths were released continuously for 3 d at 20 moths/cage (♂:♀ 1:1). A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung